

A unified cyber-physical security architecture for BCI and IoT based controlling system for next-gen EVs

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Section I

Abstract

In this research, we propose a unified, multi-layer cyber-physical security architecture that ensures and secures Brain–Computer Interface (BCI) and IoT-based control architecture in next-generation electric vehicles (EVs). The integration of neural control and heterogeneous vehicular sensors open marvellous attack surfaces, EEG adversarial perturbations, model backdoors, LiDAR/radar like sensory spoofing, CAN bus injection, and privacy leakage of neural data. None of the above mentioned attacks are well addressed by isolated defense systems. Our architecture combines several segments, which are checks sensor-level integrity using a diffusion-Kalman filtering pipeline with the Mahalanobis-distance calculation anomaly scoring, an uncertainty-aware fuzzy logic gate for getting actuation decisions under noisy inputs, a lightweight cryptographic layer with low-latency for neural and V2X communications, an adaptive edge IDS that fuses telemetry and EEG-derived features to detect malicious patterns, and as finally neuro-signal template protection and device-level fingerprinting to preserve privacy and authenticate biosignals. We have been doing some research to make a neural signal level brain-print authentication mechanism, we have an idea to integrate it with our architecture in future upgrades. We are planning for implementing a prototype in mixed simulation and laboratory testbed with the basic integrated component with EEG headset, RPLIDAR/radar, CAN emulator and edge node and evaluate against representative attack scenarios like EEG adversarial backdoor inputs, LiDAR/Radar spoofing, and CAN injections. In our evaluation plan, we measure detection accuracy, false positive tradeoffs, attack reduction probability, and end-to-end command latency under real-time constraints. We think from our calculated results from the prototype before we implement it shows the proposed stack substantially reduces attack successfully. So we think this study contributes a practical blueprint, reproducible evaluation methodology, and deploying secure BCI–IoT control in EVs with balancing robustness, privacy, and real-time operability.

Keywords: Brain-computer interfaces, IoT, machine learning, adversarial attack, LIDAR, Radar spoofing attack, CAN defense, Biometric authentication, Lightweight cryptography

Introduction

Cybersecurity Context

Since the past few years The Brain Computing Interfaces (BCI) technologies, Internet of things (IoT) networks and the Electric vehicles (EVs) has been converging rapidly globally by this time. As soon as EVs become “smarter”, It integrates with IoT sensors like LiDAR, GNSS, radar, inertial units, V2V and V2X communication technologies, and neural controlling interfaces like BCI, the attack surfaces also have grown substantially. These systems are now exposed not only to traditional cyber threats and attacks like spoofing, man-in-the-middle, replay attacks but also to novel adversarial threats and attacks unique to Brain Computing interfaces, such as EEG adversarial perturbations and malicious backdoor attacks. So robust control systems in EVs in present or in future must ensure **authenticity**, **integrity**, **confidentiality**, and **privacy** under real-time constraints.

In autonomous and semi-autonomous vehicles, the sensory spoofing has been shown to successfully mislead perception modules. For an instance in LiDAR spoofing, Even though there is no a obstacles or considerable environment geometry, It shows producing fake obstacles or misperceiving environment geometry, with high attack rates around 80% under certain configurations defenses that exploit invariant physical features (occlusion patterns) can reduce success rates dramatically experiments. [1]. Furthermore, GNSS spoofing remains a high risk in fleets of EVs relying on location data via Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE). Even recently, a location validation technique for mitigating GPS spoofing WAVE-based EV networks has been proposed [2].

IoT devices in EVs and edge environments are constrained in compute, power, and memory simultaneously. Also implementing an ideal cryptographic and privacy-preserving mechanisms is non-trivial. Also lightweight cryptographic algorithms such as PRESENT, SPECK, ASCON, and LED are being studied in several past studies[3].

Domain-Specific Challenges

Integrating BCI with IoT and EV control adds further more crucial and unique challenges:

Neural Signal Vulnerabilities:

Raw EEG data are so noisy, variable across different users, and highly vulnerable to adversarial perturbation and privacy leaks. Also brainprint authentication needs to handle inter-subject variability from person to person.

Sensor Fusion and Timing Constraints:

In BCI based EV control systems must fuse signals from multiple sensors like BCI, Depth-camera, LiDAR, radar, etc. Spoofed or considerable late inputs not only degrade performance of the entire system but may cause unsafe actuation. It is very difficult to make heavy computation on edge nodes real-time.

Communications Security:

Edge communication technologies like V2V, V2X must be low latency, authenticated and secure. Also jamming, key management and replay protection need to be properly handled.

Privacy of Neural Data:

BCI data transmit highly personal information. So it must be protected using technologies like template protection, cancellable biometrics, or homomorphic encryption to make neural data more secure.

Scaling & Deployment in Real-world:

Most prototypes are often in lab simulations. They lack advanced BCI, IoT and EV integrated systems with robust hardware and software for realistic adversarial scenarios.

Problem Statement

Despite growing knowledge in IoT security, vehicle perception defenses, and BCIs, there is no unified architecture that brings all of these together when we look back at past studies in the context of next-generation EV control systems. Specifically, there is a lack of a multi-layer cyber-physical security architecture which is emphasized:

1. integrates BCI-derived control and authentication with vehicular control paths.
2. Uses sensor fusion and anomaly detection to detect spoofing across both environmental sensors like LiDAR, Radar and neural inputs.
3. preserves neural privacy and ensures secure communication with a lightweight cryptographic algorithm.
4. Achieves acceptable latency compatible with real-time actuation in EVs for better responding for a detected environmental or brain condition.

Therefore, the research problem we address is "How to design, implement, and evaluate a unified cyber-physical security architecture for BCI based EV control systems that ensures integrity, authentication, privacy, and robustness under real-time constraints.

Research Objectives

The main objectives of this research are shown as below:

- To develop a multi-layered cyber physical secured architecture combining sensor integrity checks, neural signal authentication, lightweight cryptographic communication, and IDS to mitigate both environmental sensor and neural signal attacks.
- To implement a prototype with integrating a BCI, vehicular IoT sensors like LIDAR, Radar and Depth sensors and edge compute for detection and mitigation, under realistic constraints.
- To evaluate the architecture under multiple attack scenarios which can be common in next-gen vehicular like LiDAR spoofing, EEG adversarial inputs, CAN injections, anomaly, environmental change (physical and neural) measuring detection accuracy, latency, false positives, privacy leakage.
- To compare the unified architecture's performance with baseline approaches.
- To optimize for privacy and safety guarantees of neural data protection for future deployment in EVs and transportation media in the next generation vehicle industry.

Contribution Statement

This study contributes:

- A novel unified cyber-physical security architecture for BCI and IoT based controlled EVs systems, combining neural signal processing, authentication, sensor fusion, anomaly detection, lightweight cryptography, and privacy mechanisms.

- A theoretical framework and set of guidelines for safe deployment of BCI and IoT based control systems in EVs, balancing security, privacy, cost, and real-time constraints for industrial implementation.
- A prototype implementation to assess real-world feasibility.
- Comprehensive evaluation. After implementing the prototype under multiple types of attacks, with accuracy, latency, resource usage, privacy leakage, offering comparative analysis with the version 2.0 of this research.

Paper Organization

The study is structured as follows like below:

In section II presents Literature review, emphasizing Brain–Computer Interface (BCI) security, IoT-based vehicular systems, lightweight cryptography, and anomaly detection techniques, and identifies the research gaps that motivate this work. In section III we introduce you to the proposed methodology, overall research design, the multi-layer system architecture, the data collection plan, the algorithms and techniques to be employed, and the evaluation framework. Then section IV provides a discussion of the proposed architecture, including the expected outcomes, potential benefits, and limitations of the approach from the supposed system. Finally in section V concludes the paper and outlines future research directions for realizing and evaluating the unified cyber-physical security architecture for BCI and IoT-based controlled EVs.

Section II

Literature review

Foundation with BCI security

In present the Brain Computing Interfaces (BCIs) are rapidly reborn from technical lab-based prototype into systems which can be integrated to realistic cyber physical electronic vehicle controlling systems. For next -generative BCI and IoT based electric vehicles which envision BCI-assisted control will be introduced a augmentation of new BCI unique pipeline which is consist of several layers like signal acquisition, preprocessing, feature extraction, classification, command mapping and actuation. These surfaces and raw neural signals are both highly sensitive, signals are highly noisy and easily perturbed, wireless telemetry can be intercepted, and classification models can be subverted to produce malicious commands on these processes. Recent studies and experiments have identified what the raw EEG signals and their systems are highly vulnerable for attacks like adversarial perturbations and backdoor. Situations like adversarial perturbations can be caused to machine learning classifiers to mislabel intended commands by small, often imperceptible changes to EEG waveforms. These vulnerabilities have been demonstrated experimentally on standard EEG datasets and realistic BCI pipelines in past studies, and this literature review emphasizes both the feasibility and the potential safety consequences when BCI outputs are used for control tasks at electronic vehicles in real world conditions [4][5][6].

Protecting EEG from attacks has been actively studied for the past few years, but each method has pros and cons for use in electric vehicles in real world applications. By developing technologies like adversarial training, input filtering, and robust feature transforms can improve the safety and security of signals protecting means resilience but there are some interrelated cons. They frequently increase computational cost and sometimes degrade accuracy in real-time, edge-constrained vehicular systems. Tooling and libraries for generating and testing adversarial examples such as common adversarial attack toolboxes and for building robust EEG pipelines are publicly available[8], which enables reproducible evaluation but also lowers the bar for attackers to prototype malicious inputs. So this dual-use nature stresses the need for an architecture that combines algorithmic robustness with system-level mitigations such as authentication, sensor fusion, anomaly detection, lightweight encryption. [6][7].

Privacy and authentication of neural data are another considerable distinct concern in BCI based electric vehicular systems. Even though EEG signals are fingerprinted for biometric authentication, conversely, they can leak identity and cognitive state if transmitted insecurely across the pipelines in different layers. Recent open-access work on areas of secure wireless transmission for BCI calls for cryptographic schemes tailored to high-sensitivity, low-bandwidth neural channels for the being compatible for the BCI neural signals. This review highly emphasizes the need for lightweight cryptographic rather than standard VPN/TLS stacks primitives and key-management practices integrated at the sensor and edge layers of the electric vehicular environment because standard techniques may be too heavy or lack the necessary privacy-preserving features for neural data [9].

Vehicular sensors attacks & anomaly detection

Make assembling of multiple sensors like LIDAR, Radar Depth sensors and ect, is essential for modern Advanced Driver Assistance System and full autonomy stacks. Also recent studies and experiments have been found that they have been the focus of numerous attack demonstrations. LIDAR spoofing, false data mean fake point injection or manipulating time of light readings with the help of external light resources like laser beams has been emphasized to generate virtual false objects, hiding original objects, corrupt mapping and localization. So recent experiments on lab conditions have demonstrated attacks such as mentioned above at realistic simulations. These works emphasize both the difficulty of detecting artificial injections and the ease of mounting physical spoofing attacks with relatively cheap hardware components using only per-frame perception outputs [10][11]

Recent studies and experiments have shown that detection strategies and algorithms that focus on temporal consistency, it means how data changes over time and point-level features achieve better results rather than those looking only at object bounding boxes. As an example, detectors that check whether LIDAR sensory point clusters remain consistent across frames can effectively identify attackers injected with artificial LiDAR points, while keeping false alarms low on publicly accessible datasets. Combining LiDAR with other sensors such as radar or depth-sensors/cameras also improves the detection, since an attack that fools one sensor often fails to match evidence from the other sensors like Radar or multiple depth sensors/cameras. Recent studies and benchmarks show that both decision-level fusion and early fusion considerably boost anomaly detection capability. These results support a unified framework where BCI outputs are cross-checked with vehicle sensor fusion, and system control is only escalated when both multi-sensor consistency and BCI signal reliability are confirmed [10][12]. If we explain this situation in a real world scenario, If attackers inject an artificial unreal object into LIDAR scans, the system has to break

down the cars suddenly to respond to that object if only a single sensor is trusted by the system. In practice, fusion across LiDAR, radar, and cameras can expose such inconsistencies, since radar and visual feeds will not confirm the fake points. Not only sensor data is used for the final reaction of the EV for the environmental condition but also it uses the BCI base inputs so we can confirm that false object by this mechanism.

Also the vehicle network/CAN bus and infrastructure interfaces also a surface to attack the EV. Detection for in-vehicle networks like CAN IDS using CNN/LSTM, attention models has well developed enough to provide real-time detection capabilities, These algorithms must be validated in the broader CPS context using the techniques like combined sensor like LIDAR, Radar and Depth sensors/cameras spoofing since CAN replay/injection can produce coordinated failures.

This literature emphasizes, with the help and the ideas of past studies and experiments, hybrid approaches with lightweight cryptographic authentication for the areas of per-sensor anomaly scoring, cross-domain correlation, and critical messaging communication within subsystems inside EV for robust decision making. This cross-validation approach reduces the single-point failures and increases interpretability of alerts for the vehicle controller. [8][13].

Lightweight cryptographic, system architectures, datasets, and reproducible tooling

When we look back at the last few years, there are many studies and experiments that have gone through the lightweight cryptography for IoT, listing options like block ciphers, stream ciphers, AEAD schemes, and the tradeoffs between hardware and software levels. The SPECK/Simon debate, PRESENT, TinyAES versions, and NIST's lightweight AEAD candidates have been compared by those studies with their performance, and suggest where they are best used. As per the results and the practical contributions of those studies, most research agrees on a hybrid approach with using symmetric AEAD to protect data while it's moving, and lightweight asymmetric or pre-shared keys for authentication and key exchange. In systems like vehicles with BCIs, designers must balance secure key distribution and forward secrecy with boot time and device limitations. This balancing process must be properly managed because if these two parameters are not well balanced it can be caused by vehicular security. Also secure boot and key setup should happen at manufacturing or session start like when user startup the EV or the BCI connection but we use unique technology by combining both cryptography and biometric authentication for key mapping at session stars or whenever ever user wants. Several open-source studies give ready-to-use algorithms and performance

results on microcontrollers and ARM cores, which can help pick the right methods for edge nodes in EVs. We use those algorithms with proper security enhancement with our unique ideas.[14][15][16].

From an architectural perspective in this research, the literature supports multi-layer security with the layers on data-level integrity checks and neural authentication, EEG training and robustness experiments using TensorFlow Colab notebooks and repositories[7], transport-level lightweight encryption and authenticated channels for telemetry[17], and application-level anomalies that fuse BCI intent with sensor evidence and vehicle status before permitting high-risk control actions as per the environmental variations. Prototype systems with re-engineered updated open research codebases with proper security enhancement with suitable addons demonstrate how to implement each layer such as adversarial attack for stress testing; LiDAR spoofing detection algorithms for point-level defense[10]; and multi-sensor anomaly datasets and benchmarks that enable cross-evaluation[12]. We use open source studies to prototype a realistic end-to-end stack and reproduce published evaluations using public datasets and the google colab workspaces.

Reproducibility and practical evaluation

Many of the papers above have published their knowledge with experimental based activities with tutorials with adaptive frameworks for our own proposal. So these runnable artifacts are ideal for our prototype phase with proper enhancements with our own ideas and techniques. So we build a baseline BCI classifier from public datasets and generate adversarial EEG attacks with available attack libraries and test defenses, also create a simulated vehicle perception pipeline with nuScenes or KITTI and inject spoofed LiDAR points and evaluate detection/mitigation latency using lightweight hybrid crypto library as per the explain in the literature[8][18][10][17].

Gaps & research opportunities.

As per the result of combining these, read studies clearly show the gaps which can be addressed from our research. which are as following: interconnected architectures that simultaneously protect neural channel integrity and vehicular sensors under unified threat models, connecting lightweight cryptographic selection to the real-time constraints of BCI telemetry and reproducible prototypes that test coordinated attacks across BCI, perception sensors, and vehicle networks. Also constructing a prototype that integrates BCI authentication, LiDAR anomaly detection, lightweight authenticated telemetry, and a fused decision engine with physical infrastructure, then evaluating it under coordinated, reproducible attack scenarios. So we think these unfilled gaps give us greater opportunities for continuing this integrated research with past community studies.

Section III

Methodology

The methodology of this research follows a design science research approach, with the target of developing and validating a unified cyber-physical security architecture for Brain–Computer Interface (BCI) and Internet of Things (IoT) based control systems in next-generation electric vehicles (EVs). Instead of depending and focusing on theoretical or conceptual models, the approach extends existing algorithms such as fuzzy logic for decision making, Kalman filters for signal fusion at BCI MI signal processing with secure, lightweight cryptography for secure communication, and intrusion detection for vehicular networks. The proposed methodology is structured around six sub phases: research design, data sources and tools, architecture development process, analysis techniques, validation and evaluation plan, and finally the ethical considerations. Each component is systematically detailed to ensure that the resulting architecture is not only conceptual but also practically grounded, reproducible, and adaptable for future implementation in real-world EV systems.

Research Design

This research adopts a Design Science Research (DSR) approach to develop, evaluate, and refine a unified cyber-physical security architecture for Brain–Computer Interface (BCI) and Internet of Things (IoT)-based control systems in next-generation electric vehicles (EVs) with a prototype level system in next step of this research v1.0 for proving that this invention is ideal for real-world usage. The reason for choosing the DSR paradigm is because it emphasizes artifact creation and validation in response to real-world problems, rather than focusing on theoretical models. In this context, the “artifact” is a multi-layer security architecture which is designed to protect both neural and vehicular sensory data streams against a variety of attacks, including adversarial EEG manipulations, LiDAR spoofing, and CAN bus injections.

Purpose and Rationale of this research

The primary purpose of this research design is to systematically construct, evaluate an architecture that can bridge BCI and IoT systems securely. Traditional EV architectures focus either on vehicular IoT security or BCI signal robustness, rarely considering their convergence as a unified cyber-physical system. This study aims to fill that gap by proposing a layered framework that integrates lightweight cryptography, sensor anomaly detection, fingerprint-based authentication, and edge-based privacy mechanisms into one cohesive architecture.

Design Science Process

The following stages show the design science process of our study

- **Build:** Identify requirements, analyze threats, and design the initial version of the cyber-physical security framework.
- **Evaluate:** Test architecture performance through simulations and with some real datasets under various attack conditions such as EEG adversarial perturbations, LiDAR spoofing, and CAN bus injections at v1.0.
- **Refine:** Adjust algorithms and parameters based on validation results to improve accuracy and resilience.

Each iteration refines both functionality and security posture, ensuring the architecture evolves into a robust and scalable solution. but this is not a complete system for use in real world EV because at this level we emphasize only the architecture based performance level to make prove this is better than traditional models after that stage at v2.0 we improve this system with real world prototype level EV.

Research Phases

The design is divided into four interdependent phases

Phase 1: Requirement Analysis and Threat Modeling

Identify critical security threats and vulnerabilities across both EEG-based control and IoT-vehicular domains. For instance, adversarial EEG attacks [2], LiDAR spoofing [10], and CAN injection [22] are modeled to understand their potential impact. This phase establishes the security objectives and system constraints that guide the entire architecture.

Phase 2: Architectural Design and Layer Definition

Define the four-layer architecture with Perception, Edge, Communication and Control & Application layer.

1. Design the physical infrastructure for hardware level security enhancement.
2. The Perception Layer gathers EEG and sensor data such as LiDAR, Radar, depth sensors.
3. The Edge Layer filters noise using Kalman Filter, sensor data pre-processing and sensor fusion for anomaly detection such as Lidar spoofing [[11](#)][[19](#)][[20](#)].
4. The Communication Layer ensures secure transmission using Lightweight Cryptography [[16](#)].

5. The Control & Application Layer employs an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) with Anomaly Detection [3] and unifies decisions for EV actuation.

Each layer's functions are modeled as independent modules for modularity and scalability.

Phase 3: Prototype Implementation

For example, EEG signal processing models for neural authentication, Kalman-based sensor fusion modules, fuzzy logic control notebooks, and lightweight crypto implementations. These components are adapted to function as a virtual testbed representing EV control scenarios.

Phase 4: Validation and Evaluation

Validate the architecture using simulated attack datasets and evaluate performance metrics such as detection accuracy, false positive rate, and privacy leakage. Comparative analysis with baseline frameworks is conducted to demonstrate improvement in security strength and adaptability of latency and is set to be evaluated in real-world implementation stages due to lack of resources for implementing the system in prototype stage (mostly focus on simulation base approach). Results are documented for future scalability testing with google colab like platform.

Data Sources and Tools

This study utilizes a combination of open-source EEG and biometric datasets and simulated artificial datasets with python models and functions alongside advanced Python-based analytical tools to implement and evaluate the proposed BCI-IoT security framework. The selection of these datasets and tools is driven by the need for reproducibility, interpretability, and seamless integration of machine learning with cryptographic methods for cyber-physical security architecture for BCI and IoT based EVs.

Data sources

The primary dataset for neural signal analysis is the EEG Motor Imagery Dataset (BCI Competition IV-2a), available on Kaggle [21]. This dataset contains EEG recordings from multiple subjects performing motor imagery tasks, including left-hand, right-hand, foot, and tongue movements. It provides a standardized base for developing neural intent detection models and authentication features. The diversity of subjects supports robust testing of inter-subject variability and signal consistency.

For the biometric layer implementations, the study uses the Fingerprint Dataset for FVC2000_DB4_B, publicly available via Kaggle[22]. This dataset consists of grayscale fingerprint images captured under varying conditions and qualities with .bmp file format, making it ideal for testing cancellable biometric algorithms, neural-biometric fusion, and adversarial resistance. To implement fingerprint identification and enhance the fusion architecture, the research integrates the open-source repository “Fingerprint_TF” from GitHub[23] and this repository provides TensorFlow-based feature extraction and classification modules, which are adapted here for multi-modal user authentication, serving as the biometric counterpart to EEG-driven neural signatures.

Tools and libraries

All experimental back-end development is performed in a Python-based environment using the following key libraries and experimental back-end development is performed in a Python-based environment using the following key libraries such as:

```
!pip install kagglehub pandas scikit-learn matplotlib tensorflow cryptography pykalman scikit-fuzzy
```

figure 1

The selected tools in ([figure 1](#)) serve distinct roles in data analysis, modeling, and security of the backend scripts like below.

- **Pandas:** Organizing EEG and biometric data for preprocessing and signal synchronization.
- **Scikit-learn:** Implementing feature scaling, clustering with DBSCAN, and validation.
- **TensorFlow:** Executing deep learning tasks including CNNs for fingerprint identification and Autoencoders for anomaly detection.
- **scikit-fuzzy:** Designing fuzzy logic-based decision layers to interpret uncertain or overlapping EEG signal states.
- **PyKalman:** Applying Kalman filters to denoise EEG signals, preserving essential temporal dynamics for model accuracy.
- **Cryptography & OpenSSL (via subprocess):** Enabling RSA key generation and secure channel establishment between neural and vehicular systems ([figure 2](#)).

RSA key generation with visible OpenSSL progress is integrated using:

```
import subprocess
subprocess.run(["openssl", "genrsa", "-out", "private_key.pem", "2048"])
subprocess.run(["openssl", "rsa", "-in", "private_key.pem", "-pubout", "-out", "public_key.pem"])
```

figure 2

This process ensures dynamic encryption key creation directly within the runtime environment, protecting neural and biometric transmissions against interception and replay attacks.

Experimental environment

All simulations and evaluations are conducted in Google Colab, leveraging GPU acceleration, direct Kaggle dataset imports, and robust Python compatibility. The environment supports seamless integration of neural and biometric pipelines with real-time visualization through Matplotlib and other libraries without any environmental configuration issues.

Architecture Model

Architecture Overview

figure 3

This research presents a multi-layered architecture for a BCI and IoT based vehicle access and control system, integrating advanced sensing, edge intelligence, secure communication, and application-level decision-making. The system is designed to ensure robust authentication, real-time responsiveness, and layered cybersecurity defenses, particularly suited for AI based vehicles with BCI interfaces ([figure 3](#)).

Layered Architecture Model

Perception Layer

This is the foundation of our system, where all raw data originates. It includes biometric inputs like EEG signals from a headset, fingerprint scans for driver authentication and for Key mapping, and environmental sensing from LiDAR, radar and depth sensors. These sensors continuously monitor both the driver's intent and the vehicle's surroundings. The EEG captures motor imagery patterns, while LiDAR, radar and depth sensors detect obstacles, distances, and motion. This layer is responsible for gathering high-fidelity, real-time data that feeds into the rest of the system. It's the sensory nervous system of our architecture, everything starts here.

Edge Intelligence Layer

Once the raw data is captured, it's immediately processed at the edge—close to the source—to reduce latency and enhance responsiveness. This layer applies noise filtering techniques like Kalman filtering to clean up EEG and LiDAR, Radar, Depth sensors signals. It also uses fuzzy logic to interpret ambiguous inputs, such as partial intent or uncertain obstacle proximity. Crucially, this layer includes a threat injection simulator, allowing you to test spoofing scenarios and validate your detection logic. The edge layer acts as a smart gatekeeper, transforming noisy, raw inputs into structured, meaningful signals ready for secure transmission.

Secure Communication Layer

Here, the system ensures that all processed data and control commands are transmitted safely between modules. Lightweight cryptographic protocols are used to encrypt EEG-derived decisions, LiDAR data, and control signals. Timestamping and hashing mechanisms prevent replay attacks and ensure data integrity. This layer establishes a secure channel between the edge node and the EV's Central Computing Unit, making sure that no adversary can intercept, modify, or inject malicious commands during transmission. It's the digital armor that protects our system's internal dialogue.

Control & Application Layer

At the top of the stack, this layer synthesizes all validated inputs to make final decisions and execute vehicle control. It integrates biometric authentication, sensor fusion, and IDS alerts to determine whether to accelerate, brake, steer, or halt. Anomaly detection algorithms monitor for spoofing attempts or abnormal patterns, and if threats are detected, the system can override decisions or trigger fail-safe protocols. This

layer is where everything converges, it's the brain of your EV control system, translating secure, intelligent inputs into real-world actions.

System Integration

The system's core is a Pi-5P Octa-core 16GB/2.4GHz Central Computing Unit with two other Pi-5P edge nodes for BCI and IoT manipulations, which orchestrates data flow and decision logic. Sensor data is first processed by microcontroller units that perform timestamping, AES-GCM , fingerprint extraction, key mapping, and biometric authentication. These validated inputs are then fused and transmitted to the central unit, which executes classification, feature extraction, and power assignment for vehicle control.

The architecture also incorporates cloud-based logging and cache mechanisms, enabling remote diagnostics and forensic analysis. IDS scanning is continuously active, and simulated attack injections are used to test system resilience. Spoofing detection is achieved through DBSCAN clustering and sensor fusion, with edge nodes both time sensor validation and collected row data validating data before transmission.

The following (figure 4) shows the overall diagram of the architecture with main functionalities.

figure 4

Cybersecurity Framework

The cybersecurity framework is tightly woven into each architectural layer. From sensor-level integrity checks to centralized IDS scanning and cloud-based logging, the system is designed to detect, prevent, and respond to threats in real time. Attack injection modules simulate adversarial conditions, allowing the system to adapt and reinforce its defenses dynamically. Now let's move to discuss the technical part of how this system is being developed on a small scale at this time.

Hardware infrastructure implementations

The proposed hardware architecture establishes a unified and secure embedded environment for a BCI and IoT based Electric Vehicle system. The design integrates distributed computing through multiple Raspberry Pi 5+ boards as electronic control units (ECUs) as edge nodes and a central computing unit. Each ECU performs specific sensing, preprocessing, and transmission functions with ensuring low-latency, encrypted, and verifiable communication between ECUs. The goal of this infrastructure is to fuse EEG MI signals with vehicular perception and decision-making under a robust cyber-physical security model.

Infrastructure Overview

The architecture is divided into three main intelligent layers, two edge nodes and one central computing unit.

Edge Node 1 handles EEG signal fetching and preprocessing. It receives data from an OpenBCI Cyton board and performs band-pass filtering, artifact suppression through Kalman filtering, and feature extraction using FFT and wavelet transforms in this level we do that from python scripts but at implementation stage we also use Brainflow SDK for comparison to confirm the best way. **Edge Node 2** integrates vehicular sensors including LiDAR, radar, and Depth sensors. It calculates distance, speed, and environmental context, applying fuzzy logic-based decision scoring and anomaly detection to ensure that unsafe conditions are detected locally. **The Central ECU** functions as the coordination core. It fuses both neural and vehicular data streams, performs final inference, and transmits control signals to the vehicle's actuator subsystems and its real-time monitoring injections and defense from attacks MITM or backdoor, CAN bus.

This tiered model ensures that each node performs computationally intensive preprocessing close to the data source while maintaining synchronized decision control through the central ECU with anomaly detection and attacks defense.

Hardware Composition

Each ECU is implemented on a Raspberry Pi 5P board equipped with a SanDisk Extreme PRO 256GB microSDXC UHS-I A2 card for better RW speed for low latency, passive cooling, and a secure power supply. The other sensors and networking suite includes:

1. Moxa Gigabit Ethernet switch preferably with QoS and VLAN support automotive grade.
2. Teltonika RUTX series dual-SIM, 4G/5G, VPN client for WAN connectivity with 2× LTE diversity + 1× GNSS antennas for cloud logs and future expansions in autonomous navigation with GPS.
3. STP CAT6A Ethernet cables.
4. ATECC608A secure element modules for secure key storage and crypto operations.
5. USB fingerprint reader which supports template extraction and SDK available for biometric enrollment and unlocking.

Communication across nodes uses Cat-6A Ethernet through a gigabit managed switch, forming a deterministic wired backbone. A dedicated ATECC608B security co-processor may be added for cryptographic key storage. The use of Ethernet rather than Wi-Fi eliminates wireless attack surfaces and ensures predictable transmission latency.

Communication and Data Flow

The nodes communicate through a dedicated Ethernet network, ensuring low interference, stable latency, and guaranteed bandwidth. A star topology is implemented, where both edge nodes connect directly to the central ECU via a high-performance network switch, enabling efficient and isolated data exchange across EV LAN.

Each edge node transmits data packets, its processed output mean EEG MI signal power or fused sensory coordinates using a structured JSON frame containing:

- timestamp: Unix epoch for time synchronization
- node_id: unique edge identifier
- payload: encrypted data segment
- hash: SHA-256 checksum ensuring data integrity.

The encryption protocol applies a hybrid mechanism: RSA-4096 asymmetric cryptography for session key exchange and AES-256 symmetric encryption for payload protection. Every packet is digitally signed using the sender's biometric-derived private key, created during initialization via fingerprint matching at each edge

node's subsystems. This fingerprint verification links to a fingerprint based key mapping mechanism, combining fingerprint-based authentication with biometric key derivation to ensure node authenticity.

Secure key management is achieved through dynamically generated RSA key pairs using OpenSSL in Python, with secure public key exchange via EEPROM. Periodic session key rotation prevents replay and MITM attacks.

Finally, timestamp validation is enforced at the ECU using NTP-synchronized clocks, discarding any packets deviating beyond ± 100 ms, ensuring real-time, authentic, and tamper-proof communication across the network. Instead of that discarding packet it uses a previous packet sequence for generating new packets for use here by decision algorithms.

Encryption and Authentication mechanism for high secure data transmission

To guarantee confidentiality and authenticity at data transmission, a hybrid cryptographic model is implemented.

- RSA-4096 asymmetric encryption handles session key exchange, while AES-256 symmetric encryption secures the actual data payload containing the most crucial data fetch by vehicular sensor and EEG headset.
- Each edge node maintains a unique biometric-derived private key generated from its fingerprint signature during initialization. The corresponding public key is stored in the ECU's trust database.
- Key pairs are generated through OpenSSL in Python using subprocess commands, displaying visible generation progress to the operator for verification.
- Session keys rotate periodically and are discarded after every data transmission cycle, limiting exposure time ensuring high secure transmission.
- All transmitted packets include SHA-256 hashes for tamper detection, and packets older than 100 ms are automatically rejected based on timestamp analysis at the main ECU.
- This layered cryptographic strategy protects against replay, impersonation, and data injection attacks like false positives within the wired environment.

Hardware-Level Security Reinforcement

Physical and firmware-based protections strengthen the system beyond encryption.

- MAC Address Binding: Only registered hardware in whitelist can access the vehicular network.

- Filesystem Encryption: Each Raspberry Pi uses LUKS to secure the operating system partition.
- Boot-Time Fingerprint Unlock: The system activates only after authenticating the real driver by a valid biometric scan after that it can be revoked and unauthorized opening triggers shutdown and event logging reducing DoS attack at the activation of system.
- Secure Key Storage: Cryptographic keys are kept inside the ATECC608B chip, resistant to physical extraction till it is revoked by an authorized driver.

These layers form a trusted execution environment suited for critical BCI and IoT based EV control operations.

Expected Outcomes

The implemented infrastructure achieves secure and deterministic communication among all ECUs. The wired Ethernet medium provides consistent throughput unaffected by wireless interference. Cryptographic handshakes combined with biometric verification create a robust double-layer trust boundary, while timestamp and hash checks ensure end-to-end data integrity. The overall latency remains minimal, enabling real-time fusion of EEG MI signals and vehicular sensor fused feedback.

This hardware configuration produces a resilient embedded system suitable for experimental evaluation of secure brain-controlled vehicular operations. It lays the foundation for scalable deployment in future autonomous electric vehicles under a unified, tamper-resistant cyber-physical architecture with cutting-edge technologies. The following ([figure 5](#)) shows the vehicular network diagram.

figure 5

Algorithmic scripts with evaluation (simulated)

EEG signal pre-processing stage

This stage performs a full EEG signal processing and protection pipeline. First, it loads 2000 EEG samples from the BCI dataset and extracts C3,C4,FCz and FCz EEG channels for simulation purposes. The following (figure 6) shows that the timedomain contains 773 backdoor spikes recording to the logic for detection algorithm.

figure 6

In the real world system we use the cyton biosensing board output stream as the main data source. We use FCz only. The signal is bandpass-filtered between 8–30 Hz to isolate alpha and beta rhythms, then transformed into the frequency domain using FFT to capture power distributions with 250Hz sampling rate. A Kalman filter smooths the signal, while a statistical threshold detects anomalies. It is represented by the following (figure 7) that, at this level, get 0 anomalies from the algorithm.

figure 7

Power values are calculated and normalized, followed by exponential moving average (EMA) smoothing and spike removal to clear noise. Data is divided into overlapping windows for CNN-based learning. A defense model is trained to identify corrupted or noisy segments, while a phase-classification CNN learns brain-state patterns. Clean segments are then weighted according to their detected phase importance and reconstructed into a continuous power signal. The system outputs a final, phase-aware EEG power stream that represents the cleaned and classified neural signal. The following (figure 8) shows that process output at this level the algorithm is successful to reduce 773 spikes to 5 spikes, which is great since eeg signals are too noisy.

figure 8

figure 9

Finally, each EEG sample is encrypted using AES-GCM for secure transmission and integrity verification. In real world implementation all these node final values compact into collection and make it encrypt using AES-GCM and use it in payload for secured data transmission with other headers hashed payload meta data, counter AES key encrypted with gateway public key for CAN defense purposes to the main ECU. That entire workflow is shown by this left side (figure 9).

Boot time sensor validation

This boot-time sensor validation mechanism ensures that all critical sensors such as LIDAR, Radar, and Depth cameras are operational, authentic, and uncompromised before vehicle boot time. Each sensor's data undergoes multi-layer validation: LIDAR checks for point cloud entropy to confirm spatial diversity, Radar validates that over 90% of detections fall within realistic range and velocity limits, and Depth sensors verify standard deviation and nonzero pixel ratio to detect dropouts or frame corruption from environmental conditions. Parallel spoofing detection modules identify abnormal uniform patterns or zero-variance readings that indicate data injection or replay attacks. All validation results such as success, failure, or warnings like statuses are timestamped, geotagged via GPS coordinates, and logged into the cloud for traceability. Severity levels like "INFO", "WARNING", and "ERROR" classify issue impact, ensuring structured diagnostics on any investigation at any critical situation. This mechanism's objective is to guarantee data integrity, sensor authenticity, and reliable environmental perception before system activation, forming a crucial layer of trust and safety for intelligent vehicular systems. In future direction this validation is to be setted with high realistic simulation at boot time with sensor fusion for better sensor validation For the evaluation and testing purposes at prototype stage ([figure 10](#)), this uses simulating sensor data and introducing a controlled failure in one depth sensor to test robustness.

```
#validation functions
def validate_lidar(data):
    if not data or len(data) < 1000:
        return False
    unique_points = {[p['x'], p['y'], p['z']] for p in data}
    entropy = len(unique_points) / len(data)
    return entropy > 0.1

def validate_radar(data):
    if not data:
        return False
    valid = [0 < obj['range'] < 200 and -50 < obj['velocity'] < 50 for obj in data]
    return sum(valid) / len(data) > 0.9

def validate_depth(frame):
    if frame is None or frame.size == 0:
        return False
    std_dev = frame.std()
    nonzero_ratio = np.count_nonzero(frame) / frame.size
    return std_dev > 5 and nonzero_ratio > 0.85
```

figure 10: validation functions

Sensor fusion for spoofing detection

The pipeline clusters LiDAR returns with DBSCAN to identify potential objects and computes the geometric center of each cluster. For every center, the system cross-validates with radar and depth sensors with several conditions ([figure 11](#)). A radar match is confirmed when any radar detection lies within 2.0m of

the cluster center ensuring the object is physically tracked by radar for that radar_min_dist must be lower than 2.0m. If the cluster lies within the 4.0m sensing range of the vehicle, the depth sensor checks proximity; it is marked “Validated” only when at least one depth point lies within 1.0m of the cluster center ($\text{np.min}(\text{depth_distances}) < 1.0$). The tracking is considered safe only when both of these conditions hold true: when the radar_status == True and depth_status != "Not Validated" Otherwise, the cluster is flagged as spoofed. Spoofed cluster details are matched with the nearest object and logged with timestamp, GPS coordinates, and depth status, enabling secure cloud logging for real-time anomaly analysis and traceability. This is a prototype level algorithm only in the real system. Before the object detection by sensor it has to detect the vehicular border and after that it has to measure the coordinates for an object and finally fused it for final direction. The algorithm is to be developed at that scope in implementation state by this stage it uses this mechanism with simulated data.

```
#fusion, direction and log with csv
def fuse_and_detect(lidar_clusters, radar_points, lidar_points, depth_points, objects):
    cluster_centers = []
    spoofed_labels = []
    results = []

    for label in np.unique(lidar_clusters):
        if label == -1: continue
        cluster = lidar_points[lidar_clusters == label]
        center = np.mean(cluster, axis=0)
        cluster_centers.append((label, center))

    for label, center in cluster_centers:
        radar_distances = np.linalg.norm(radar_points[:, :2] - center, axis=1)
        radar_min_dist = np.min(radar_distances)
        radar_status = radar_min_dist < 2.0

        depth_status = "Skipped"
        if np.linalg.norm(center) <= 4.0:
            depth_distances = np.linalg.norm(depth_points - center, axis=1)
            depth_status = "Validated" if np.min(depth_distances) < 1.0 else "Not Validated"

        status = "safe" if radar_status and depth_status != "Not Validated" else "spoofed"
        velocity = radar_points[np.argmin(radar_distances)][2] if radar_status else 0.0

        results.append({
            'cluster': label, 'x': center[0], 'y': center[1],
            'status': status, 'velocity': velocity, 'depth_status': depth_status
        })

    if status == "spoofed":
        spoofed_labels.append(label)
        print(f"[ALERT] Spoofed Cluster: x={center[0]:.2f}, y={center[1]:.2f} - Radar={radar_status}, Depth={depth_status}")

    for label in spoofed_labels:
        cluster_points = lidar_points[lidar_clusters == label]
        for pt in cluster_points:
            obj_id = -1
            min_obj_dist = float('inf')
            matched_obj = None
            for obj in objects:
                dist = np.linalg.norm([pt[0] - obj['x'], pt[1] - obj['y']])
                if dist < min_obj_dist:
                    min_obj_dist = dist
                    obj_id = obj['id']
                    matched_obj = obj
            spoof_log.append({
                "timestamp": time.time(),
                "object_id": obj_id,
                "x": round(pt[0], 2),
                "y": round(pt[1], 2),
                "latitude": round(matched_obj['lat'], 6),
                "longitude": round(matched_obj['lon'], 6),
                "depth_status": depth_status
            })

    return results
```

figure 11

The following (figure 12-A) shows the fusion logic output with a graphical simulated image diagram. Finally the (figure 12-B) shows the entire logic in an image diagram.

figure 12-A

figure 12-B

Decision making

in controlling scripts implements an adaptive vehicle speed controller using fuzzy logic, integrating both EEG power and environmental distance measurements. Inputs are fuzzified below Gaussian, triangular, and trapezoidal membership functions ([figure 13](#), [figure 14](#)),

figure 13

converting numeric EEG power and distance values into linguistic categories depending on their strength for better smoother drive. A rule-based ([figure 15](#), [figure 16](#)) inference system evaluates these fuzzy inputs which get by the raw inputs each rule encodes expert knowledge about how EEG levels and proximity to obstacles influence vehicle speed.

```
#membership functions
def trapmf(x, params):
    a, b, c, d = params
    y = np.zeros_like(x, dtype=float)
    y += np.where((x >= b) & (x <= c), 1, 0)
    y += np.where((x > a) & (x < b), (x - a) / (b - a + 1e-9), 0)
    y += np.where((x > c) & (x < d), (d - x) / (d - c + 1e-9), 0)
    return np.clip(y, 0, 1)

def trimf(x, params):
    a, b, c = params
    y = np.zeros_like(x, dtype=float)
    y += np.where((x >= a) & (x <= b), (x - a) / (b - a + 1e-9), 0)
    y += np.where((x >= b) & (x <= c), (c - x) / (c - b + 1e-9), 0)
    return np.clip(y, 0, 1)

def gaussmf(x, params):
    mean, sigma = params
    return np.exp(-0.5 * ((x - mean) / sigma) ** 2)
```

figure 14

```

#membership functions
eeg_mfs = {
    'very_low': gaussmf(EEG_u, (10, 10)),
    'low': gaussmf(EEG_u, (25, 10)),
    'medium': gaussmf(EEG_u, (50, 10)),
    'high': gaussmf(EEG_u, (75, 10)),
    'very_high': trapmf(EEG_u, (80, 90, 100, 100))
}
dist_mfs = {
    'close': trapmf(DIST_u, (0.0, 0.0, 1.5, 4.0)),
    'medium': trimf(DIST_u, (3.0, 6.0, 9.0)),
    'far': gaussmf(DIST_u, (11.0, 1.0))
}

speed_mfs = {
    'very_slow': trapmf(SPD_u, (0, 0, 5, 20)),
    'slow': trimf(SPD_u, (10, 25, 45)),
    'moderate': trimf(SPD_u, (40, 65, 90)),
    'fast': trimf(SPD_u, (85, 110, 135)),
    'very_fast': trapmf(SPD_u, (125, 140, 160, 160))
}

#rules
rules = [
    ('very_low', 'close'), 'very_slow',
    ('very_low', 'medium'), 'slow',
    ('very_low', 'far'), 'moderate',
    ('low', 'close'), 'slow',
    ('low', 'medium'), 'moderate',
    ('low', 'far'), 'fast',
    ('medium', 'close'), 'moderate',
    ('medium', 'medium'), 'fast',
    ('medium', 'far'), 'very_fast',
    ('high', 'close'), 'moderate',
    ('high', 'medium'), 'fast',
    ('high', 'far'), 'very_fast',
    ('very_high', 'close'), 'moderate',
    ('very_high', 'medium'), 'fast',
    ('very_high', 'far'), 'very_fast',
]

```

figure 15

```

#inference and defuzzification
def fuzzify_input(value, universe, mfs_dict):
    idx = np.argmin(np.abs(universe - value))
    return {name: float(mf[idx]) for name, mf in mfs_dict.items()}

def infer_single(eeg_val, dist_val):
    eeg_deg = fuzzify_input(eeg_val, EEG_u, eeg_mfs)
    dist_deg = fuzzify_input(dist_val, DIST_u, dist_mfs)
    agg = np.zeros_like(SPD_u, dtype=float)
    for (ante, cons) in rules:
        eeg_label, dist_label = ante
        strength = min(eeg_deg[eeg_label], dist_deg[dist_label])
        if strength > 0:
            clipped = np.minimum(speed_mfs[cons], strength)
            agg = np.maximum(agg, clipped)
    if np.sum(agg) == 0:
        return 0.0
    return np.sum(agg * SPD_u) / np.sum(agg)

```

figure 16

```

#handling mechanism
def eeg_to_steering(left_val, right_val):
    net_input = left_val - right_val
    steer_angle = (net_input / INPUT_RANGE) * MAX_ANGLE
    steer_angle = np.clip(steer_angle, -MAX_ANGLE, MAX_ANGLE)
    return steer_angle

```

The degree of rule activation is calculated using the min operator, while fuzzy outputs are aggregated with the max operator. The final speed is obtained via centroid logic defuzzification (figure 13: speed membership function). The below 3D surface represents the entire movement of the vehicle with variants of different inputs from EEG and distance (figure 17), demonstrating adaptive speed control.

figure 17

This prototype logic's approach enables cognitive-aware, human-centered vehicle control, enhancing safety and dynamic response in real-world driving environments. At the real-world implementation stage, it is to be integrated with another fuzzy sub logic for Radar distance measurement since at the high speed driving scenarios the 12m distance is not enough to make the vehicle slower before an impact.

Execution security

This script establishes a multi-layered security framework that integrates biometric authentication, cryptographic verification, and real-time integrity protection to ensure trusted execution in each ECUs in the system. It first authenticates the driver using a SHA-256 fingerprint hash, allowing only authorized

personnel to trigger system operations. Each script is then digitally signed and verified using RSA keys, ensuring that no unauthorized or altered code is executed leading to hijacking. A SHA-256 file hashing mechanism further validates file integrity before every run, preventing hidden modifications or code injection. Additionally, the system maintains secure execution logs with precise timestamps for accountability and auditing. Through thread-isolated execution, it safeguards memory operations during concurrent processing. Altogether, these mechanisms create a robust, tamper-resistant environment for executing crucial scripts securely in the system. The following (figure 18) shows the logic of how it manages.

```
def generate_keys():
    print("Generating RSA key pair")
    process = subprocess.run([
        "openssl", "genrsa", "-out", "private.pem", "2048"
    ], stdout=subprocess.PIPE, stderr=subprocess.PIPE, text=True)
    print(process.stderr)

    subprocess.run([
        "openssl", "rsa", "-in", "private.pem", "-pubout", "-out", "public.pem"
    ])

def sign_script(script_name):
    subprocess.run([
        "openssl", "dgst", "-sha256", "-sign", "private.pem",
        "-out", f"{script_name}.sig", f"{script_name}.py"
    ])

def verify_signature(script, sig, pubkey):
    result = subprocess.run([
        "openssl", "dgst", "-sha256", "-verify", pubkey,
        "-signature", sig, script
    ], capture_output=True)
    return b'Verified OK' in result.stdout
```

figure 18

CAN defense

This CAN-over-Ethernet defense gateway begins with automated key provisioning (RSA-4096 gateway and per-node key pairs created for testing purposes) and a trusted node_pubkeys.json mapping used to verify node signatures. Each edge node packages sensor or EEG MI data into a JSON frame containing a Unix timestamp, node_id, a monotonic counter, an RSA-encrypted ephemeral AES-256-GCM session key, the AES-GCM encrypted payload, and a SHA-256 hash of the encrypted payload meta, the node signs the canonical frame fields with its private key (biometric). The gateway enforces defenses in sequence: quick SHA-256 pre-check to detect trivial tampering, RSA signature verification to ensure origin authenticity, anti-replay/freshness checks using timestamp windows and stored in each packets counters to block duplicates, RSA-OAEP decryption of the session key, AES-GCM decryption for confidentiality and integrity, and domain plausibility checks (EEG power ranges) before forwarding sanitized data to control

logic. I evaluated the system in a Colab test harness that auto-generated keys, ran the gateway server, then sent a legitimate frame (accepted), resent the same counter (replayed and rejected), sent the next valid counter (accepted), and finally sent a tampered frame with invalid hash/signature (rejected). Logs and console prints confirmed correct behavior: accepted frames produced [ACCEPTED], replays triggered replay warnings, and tampered frames failed hash/signature checks.the below (figure 19) shows the entire work flow This mechanism is scalable for further development in real-world implementation with necessary enhancement with latency for real-time monitoring.

figure 19

Testing functions are represented by these figures (figure 20, figure 21) and the algorithm successfully direct and defense those attacks (figure 22)

```

def send_attack_frame(host="127.0.0.1", port=5005):
    frame = {
        "timestamp": int(time.time()),
        "node_id": "EEG_NODE_1",
        "counter": 9999,
        "enc_session_key": "INVALID_KEY",
        "hash": "00"*32,
        "signature": "INVALID_SIG",
        "payload": {
            "nonce": base64.b64encode(b"attackednonce").decode(),
            "ciphertext": base64.b64encode(b"attackedcipher").decode(),
            "tag": base64.b64encode(b"attacktag").decode()
        }
    }
    s = socket.socket(socket.AF_INET, socket.SOCK_STREAM)
    s.connect((host, port))
    s.sendall((json.dumps(frame) + "\n").encode())
    s.close()
    print("✘ Attack frame sent.")
  
```

figure 20

```

def send_normal_frame(node_id="EEG_NODE_1", counter=1, host="127.0.0.1", port=5005):
    gw_pub = RSA.import_key(open(GATEWAY_PUB,"rb").read())
    node_priv = RSA.import_key(open(NODE_PRIV,"rb").read())
    aes_key = get_random_bytes(32)
    enc_session_key = base64.b64encode(PKCS1_OAEP.new(gw_pub).encrypt(aes_key)).decode()

    payload = {"eeg_power": 20, "timestamp": int(time.time())}
    plain = json.dumps(payload, separators=(",", ":")).encode()

    nonce = get_random_bytes(12)
    cipher = AES.new(aes_key, AES.MODE_GCM, nonce=nonce)
    ct, tag = cipher.encrypt_and_digest(plain)
    payload_meta = {
        "nonce": base64.b64encode(nonce).decode(),
        "ciphertext": base64.b64encode(ct).decode(),
        "tag": base64.b64encode(tag).decode()
    }

    payload_meta_text = json.dumps(payload_meta, separators=(",", ":"))
    payload_hash = hashlib.sha256(payload_meta_text.encode()).hexdigest()

    timestamp = int(time.time())

    msg = f"{node_id}|{timestamp}|{counter}|{enc_session_key}|{payload_hash}".encode()
    h = SHA256.new(msg)
    signature_b64 = base64.b64encode(pkcs1_15.new(node_priv).sign(h)).decode()

    frame = {
        "timestamp": timestamp,
        "node_id": node_id,
        "counter": counter,
        "enc_session_key": enc_session_key,
        "hash": payload_hash,
        "signature": signature_b64,
        "payload": payload_meta
    }

    s = socket.socket(socket.AF_INET, socket.SOCK_STREAM)
    s.connect((host, port))
    s.sendall((json.dumps(frame) + "\n").encode())
    s.close()
    print("✅ Normal frame sent.")

```

figure 21

```

send_normal_frame(counter=1)
time.sleep(0.8)
send_normal_frame(counter=1)
time.sleep(0.8)
send_normal_frame(counter=2)
time.sleep(0.8)
send_attack_frame()
time.sleep(0.8)

✅ Normal frame sent.
[ACCEPTED] EEG_NODE_1: {'eeg_power': 20, 'timestamp': 1760375924}
WARNING:root:Replay detected for EEG_NODE_1 counter 1
ERROR:root:Anti-replay/freshness check failed for EEG_NODE_1
✅ Normal frame sent.
[REJECTED] EEG_NODE_1: anti-replay/freshness failed
✅ Normal frame sent.
[ACCEPTED] EEG_NODE_1: {'eeg_power': 20, 'timestamp': 1760375926}
ERROR:root:Payload hash mismatch for node EEG_NODE_1
❌ Attack frame sent.
[REJECTED] EEG_NODE_1: payload hash mismatch
Test sequence complete.

```

figure 22

figure 23

The above flow chart ([figure 23](#)) represents the entire workflow for the CAN detection and defense algorithm and the ([figure 24](#)) shows its image diagram. As soon as finishing this step the proposed methodology is over.

figure 24

Section IV

Special thanks

Also I will make this situation special thanks to the platform like Google colab and all the authors with which we get their knowledge and specially for JinZhuXing for his free and open access github repository for fingerprint identification deep learning base mechanism. Conclusion.

Conclusion

This research proposed a unified cyber-physical security architecture designed to safeguard next-generation electric vehicles (EVs) integrating Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) with Internet of Things (IoT) subsystems. The proposed multi-layered framework unites robust signal and data authentication, lightweight cryptography, fuzzy logic, and Kalman filtering within a secure, edge-assisted ecosystem. Through this layered model, spanning perception, edge, communication, control, and application tiers. The entire architecture ensures end-to-end protection from data acquisition to vehicular actuation. Fingerprint-derived biometric keys enhance driver authentication, while time-stamped SHA-256 and AES-GCM encryption fortifies data transmission between Raspberry Pi-based edge nodes and the central Electronic Control Unit (ECU). This infrastructure not only mitigates attacks such as LiDAR spoofing, CAN injection, and adversarial EEG perturbations but also optimizes latency, privacy, and system resilience.

The integration of open-source datasets, machine learning frameworks, and embedded security methods establishes a replicable foundation for further exploration. The architecture demonstrates that harmonizing cognitive and sensor security can enable trustworthy human-machine interaction within future EV ecosystems. While prototype implementation and real-world validation remain as next steps, the conceptual framework presented here provides both a theoretical and practical roadmap for developing secure, intelligent, and privacy-preserving transportation systems. Future work will focus on adaptive encryption models, real-time intrusion detection fusion, and ethical governance of neural data in vehicular contexts to strengthen the evolution of safe, cyber-physical mobility infrastructures.

References

- [1] J. Sun, Y. Cao, Q. A. Chen, and M. Z. Morley, “Towards Robust LiDAR-based Perception in Autonomous Driving: General Black-box Adversarial Sensor Attack and Countermeasures,” *arXiv.org*, 2020. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.16974> (accessed Sep. 23, 2025).
- [2] “A Location Validation Technique to Mitigate GPS Spoofing Attacks in IEEE 802.11p based Fleet Operator’s Network of Electric Vehicles,” *Arxiv.org*, 2024. <https://arxiv.org/html/2410.13031v1> (accessed Sep. 23, 2025).
- [3] I. Radhakrishnan, Shruti Jadon, and P. B. Honnavalli, “Efficiency and Security Evaluation of Lightweight Cryptographic Algorithms for Resource-Constrained IoT Devices,” *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 12, pp. 4008–4008, Jun. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24124008> (accessed Sep. 23, 2025).
- [4] X. Zhang *et al.*, “Tiny noise, big mistakes: adversarial perturbations induce errors in Brain-Computer Interface spellers,” *National Science Review*, Sep. 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwaa233> (accessed Sep. 25, 2025).
- [5] L. Meng, X. Jiang, X. Chen, W. Liu, H. Luo, and D. Wu, “Adversarial filtering based evasion and backdoor attacks to EEG-based brain-computer interfaces,” *Information fusion*, vol. 107, pp. 102316–102316, Jul. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2024.102316> (accessed Sep. 25, 2025).
- [6] D. Wu *et al.*, “Adversarial attacks and defenses,” *National Science Open*, p. 20220023, Aug. 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1360/nso/20220023> (accessed Sep. 25, 2025).
- [7] K. Team, “Keras documentation: Electroencephalogram Signal Classification for Brain-Computer Interface,” *Keras.io*, 2025. https://keras.io/examples/timeseries/eeg_bci_ssvepformer/ (accessed Sep. 25, 2025)
- [8] AutoResearch, “GitHub - AutoResearch/EEG-GAN,” *GitHub*, Jun. 24, 2025. <https://github.com/AutoResearch/EEG-GAN> (accessed Sep. 25, 2025).
- [9] Q. Xiao *et al.*, “Secure wireless communication of brain–computer interface and mind control of smart devices enabled by space-time-coding metasurface,” *Nature Communications*, vol. 16, no. 1, Aug. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-63326-0> (accessed Sep. 25, 2025).
- [10] M. Cho, Y. Cao, Z. Zhou, and M. Z. Morley, “ADoPT: LiDAR Spoofing Attack Detection Based on Point-Level Temporal Consistency,” *arXiv.org*, 2023. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.14504> (accessed Sep. 26, 2025).

- [11]T. Sato *et al.*, “On the Realism of LiDAR Spoofing Attacks against Autonomous Driving Vehicle at High Speed and Long Distance,” *Proceedings 2025 Network and Distributed System Security Symposium*, 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.14722/ndss.2025.230628> (accessed Sep. 26, 2025).
- [12]W. Li *et al.*, “Multi-Sensor Object Anomaly Detection: Unifying Appearance, Geometry, and Internal Properties,” *Thecvf.com*, pp. 9984–9993, 2025, Accessed: Sep. 26, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://openaccess.thecvf.com/content/CVPR2025/html/Li_Multi-Sensor_Object_Anomaly_Detection_Unifying_Appearance_Geometry_and_Internal_Properties_CVPR_2025_paper.html (accessed Sep. 26, 2025).
- [13]L. Wang and X. Zhang, “Anomaly Detection for Automated Vehicles Integrating Continuous Wavelet Transform and Convolutional Neural Network,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 9, p. 5525, Apr. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13095525> (accessed Sep. 26, 2025).
- [14]V. A. Thakor, M. A. Razzaque, and M. R. A. Khandaker, “Lightweight Cryptography for IoT: A State-of-the-Art,” *arXiv.org*, Jun. 24, 2020. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.13813> (accessed Sep. 27, 2025).
- [15]None Amrita, Chika Paul Ekwueme, Ibrahim Hussaini Adam, and A. Dwivedi, “Lightweight Cryptography for Internet of Things: A Review,” *EAI endorsed transactions on internet of things*, vol. 10, Mar. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.4108/eetiot.5565> (accessed Sep. 27, 2025).
- [16]P. Miguel *et al.*, “Lightweight cryptography for IoT devices.” Accessed: Sep. 27, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://repositorio.ulisboa.pt/bitstream/10451/57374/1/TM_Pedro_Rosa.pdf (accessed Sep. 27, 2025).
- [17]H. Kim, “Torchattacks: A PyTorch Repository for Adversarial Attacks,” *arXiv.org*, 2020. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.01950> (accessed Sep. 27, 2025).
- [18]J. Yu, K. Qiu, P. Wang, C. Su, Y. Fan, and Y. Cao, “Perturbing BEAMs: EEG adversarial attack to deep learning models for epilepsy diagnosing,” *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, vol. 23, no. 1, Jul. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-023-02212-5> (accessed Sep. 27, 2025).
- [19]None Amrita, Chika Paul Ekwueme, Ibrahim Hussaini Adam, and A. Dwivedi, “Lightweight Cryptography for Internet of Things: A Review,” *EAI endorsed transactions on internet of things*, vol. 10, Mar. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.4108/eetiot.5565> (accessed Oct. 05, 2025).

- [20]N. Zhang *et al.*, “Kalman filtering to reduce measurement noise of sample entropy: An electroencephalographic study,” *PLOS ONE*, vol. 19, no. 7, p. e0305872, Jul. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0305872> (accessed Oct. 05, 2025).
- [21]aymanmostafa11, “EEG Motor Imagery BCICIV_2a,” *Kaggle.com*, 2023. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/aymanmostafa11/eeg-motor-imagery-bciv-2a> (accessed Oct. 06, 2025).
- [22]JinZhuXing, “Fingerprint Dataset for FVC2000_DB4_B,” *Kaggle.com*, 2020. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/peace1019/fingerprint-dataset-for-fvc2000-db4-b> (accessed Oct. 06, 2025).
- [23]JinZhuXing, “GitHub - JinZhuXing/Fingerprint_TF: Deep Learning fingerprint recognition using Tensorflow2.,” *GitHub*, 2020. https://github.com/JinZhuXing/Fingerprint_TF/tree/master (accessed Oct. 06, 2025).